

NOTES

2. *For Res.*, 1941, 4299; MANZOOR-I-KHUDA *Sci. Ind.*, 1963, 1, 218; G. S. PENDSE, N. L. PHALNIKAR and B. V. BHIDE, *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 37; V. G. GOKHALE and B. V. BHIDE, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1945, 22, 250; L. CROMBIE, A. H. A. KRASINSKI and MANZOOR-I-KHUDA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4970; E. GERBER, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1903, 236, 270; M. ASANO and T. KANEMATSU, *Chem. Ber.*, 1932, 65, 1502; M. JACOBSON, *Chem. Ind.*, 1957, 50.

Phytochemical Examination of *Cressa cretica* Linn. (Rudanti)

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IN view of the medicinal importance¹ of *Cressa cretica* Linn. (Fam.: Convulvulaceae), we undertook a systematic chemical investigation of the plant.

The air-dried, powdered whole plant of *C. cretica* was extracted successively with petroleum ether, acetone, ethyl acetate and ethanol. From the petroleum ether extract after chromatographed over silica gel and elution with petroleum ether a crystalline compound, m.p. 82°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 450 (OH), 715 and 725 cm^{-1} (n-alkyl chain)² was isolated and identified as n-octacosanol (1) by the usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc, co-ir). From the chloroform-benzene (1:1) eluent of the chromatogram β -sitosterol (2), m.p. 137° was isolated (identified from its m.m.p., ¹H nmr).

The acetone extract after chromatography and elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1) gave colourless needles, m.p. 202°, which was identified as scopoletin (3) from its ir, uv and ¹H nmr spectra. From the benzene-ethyl acetate (4:1) eluent a crystalline solid, m.p. 231–32°, was isolated and identified as umbelliferone (4) from its ir, uv and ¹H nmr spectra and usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir). The ethyl acetate-chloroform (1:1) eluent gave yellow needles, m.p. 150°, which was identified as isopimpinellin (5) from its uv, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectra.

The concentrated ethyl acetate extract of the plant on cooling gave a crystalline compound, m.p. 290°, which on acid hydrolysis gave β -sitosterol and D(+)-glucose, identified by paper chromatography. Identity of the compound as β -sitosterol-D(+)-glucoside (6) was confirmed from its ¹H nmr and mass spectra.

The concentrated ethanol extract after chromatography (silica ge) and elution with ethyl acetate

gave a yellow solid, m.p. 312.15°; $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 370 nm, which was identified as quercetin (7) from its colour reactions, uv data (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir).

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References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956; V.G. APTE, "Rajaniḡhantusahto Dhanyantiariyanighantu", Anand Ashrama Mudranska, Varanasi, 1925, p. 341; K. K. PURSHOTTAM, S. CHANDRASEKARAN, M. VENKATESAN and V. NARAYANASWAMI, *J. Res. Indian Med.*, 1972, 7, 78; K. K. PURSHOTTAM and K. KALYANI, *R. Res. Indian Med.*, 1974, 9, 109; S. SATAKOPAN and G. K. KARANDIKAR, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. (C)*, 1961, 20, 156.
2. G. MISHRA, S. K. NIGAM and C. R. MITRA, *Phytochemistry*, 1969, 8, 2255.

Isorhamnetin 3-O-Rutinoside from *Syzygium cumini* Linn.

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THE plant *Syzygium cumini* Linn. (commonly known as *Jamun* in Hindi) is used as medicine for several diseases¹. Several common flavonoids², kaempferol, quercetin, myricetin, isoquercetin and isoprenoids³, oleanolic acid and betulinic acid have been reported by various workers. The present work was undertaken to reveal the presence of other biodynamic constituents.

Experimental

The roots of the plant were collected from village Khaira (District Bilaspur) in the month of October 1988 and were authenticated⁴. The shade-dried crude material (80 kg) was extracted by boiling ethanol and the *in vacuo* concentrated extract was partitioned between water and different organic solvents (from non-polar to polar). The ethyl acetate extract after repeated column chromatography over silica gel gave a compound which was homogeneous to tlc, hRf 20 (30% AcOH), 60 (BAW) on cellulose plates, m.p. 182°, and was found to be a flavonoid glycoside by usual tests⁵; $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 253, 267sh, 355; (+NaOMe) 270, 299sh, 409; (+AlCl₃) 270, 299sh, 407; (+AlCl₃/

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HCl) 270, 298sh, 405; (+NaOAc) 272, 346, 382; (+NaOAc/H₃BO₃) 257, 354 mm; δ (90 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 6.25, 6.4 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz each, H-6 and H-8), 6.94 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-5'), 7.5 (1H, dd, *J* 2, 8 Hz, H-6'), 7.98 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-2'), 3.85 (3H, s, oMe), 5.82 (1H, d, *J* 6 Hz, H-1''), 4.3 (1H, s, H-1''), 3.1–4.0 (rhamnoglucosyl 10 protons) and 0.8–1.1 (1H, m, rhamnosyl methyl).

The chemical degradations of the glycoside were made by the reported methods⁶. It revealed the presence of Rutinosyl moiety at position-3, which was also supported by the anomeric proton signals at δ 5.82 (diaxial coupling) and the rest of the sugar portion at δ 4.3 and 0.8–1.1 (m) in its pmr spectrum. The aglycone (obtained by its acidic hydrolysis), m.p. 304–06°, C₁₆H₁₂O₇, M⁺ 316, was confirmed as isorhamnetin by comparing its uv, pmr and mass spectral data⁷.

The compound was thus assigned as isorhamnetin 3-O-rutinoside which is comparatively rare in nature and is being reported for the first time in Myrtaceae family. Its occurrence is of good taxonomic interest and owing to the vast structural variation among the anthoxanthins, throws light towards the direction of secondary metabolites.

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References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p 238; B. N. DHAWAN, G. K. PATNAIK, R. B. RASTOGI, K. K. SINGH and J. S. TANDON, *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1977, 15, 208.
2. A. G. R. NAIR and S. S. SUBRAMANIAN, *J. Sci. Ind. Res., Sect. B*, 1962, 21, 457.
3. P. B. R. MURTI and N. V. S. RAO, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1945, 20, 163; P. SENGUPTA and P. B. DAS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 255.
4. Authenticated by Principal Dr. H. N. TEWARY.
5. K. VENKATRAMAN in "The Chemistry of Flavonoid Compounds", ed. T. A. GEISSMAN, Pergamon, Oxford, 1970, pp. 72, 73.
6. K. R. MARKHAM, "Technique of Flavonoid Identification", Academic, London, 1982, pp. 62-71.
7. T. J. MABRY, K. R. MARKHAM and M. B. THOMAS, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoid", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1970, pp. 138, 298; L. E. URBATCH, J. D. BALCON and T. J. MABRY, *Phytochemistry*, 1975, 14, 2279.

2-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime as an Analytical Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(III) and Fluoride†

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2-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime (2-HANO) has been found to give a greenish violet complex with iron(III) of 1 : 2 (metal-ligand) composition which absorbs maximally at 600 nm, the absorbance maximum of the reagent alone being 320 nm. This colour reaction has been used for the determination of iron(III), and indirectly for fluoride.

Experimental

Preparation of reagent: 2-Naphthol was converted into 2-naphthyl acetate by treating it with acetic anhydride¹. This compound was subjected to Fric's rearrangement²⁻⁴ as recommended by Joshi and Shah⁴ and the resulting mixture was steam-distilled when 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone was obtained in good yield. The oxime of this compound was prepared by refluxing the ketone with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in the presence of sodium acetate.

Preparation of 1-HANO: The first step, i.e. preparation of 2-acetyl-1-naphthol was conducted by the use of Nencki reaction with 1-naphthol⁵, and the reported oxime of the ketone was prepared according to the reported procedure⁶.

All the reagents were of AnalaR grade. Stock solution of iron(III) (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving ammonium ferric sulphate in distilled water.

Stock solution of fluoride (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from sodium fluoride. Sulphuric acid (0.05 M) was used to maintain the pH.

A Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer was used for measuring absorbance. pH was measured using an Elico pH meter.

Determination of iron(III): Aliquots of iron(III) (1–50 μ g) and 2-HANO (0.025 M; 5 ml) were mixed and shaken well. To it sulphuric acid (0.05 M; 10 ml) was added and the solution was made upto 25 ml with distilled water, the final pH being 3.5. The absorbance of solutions was measured after 10 min at 600 nm against the reagent blank.

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